

MODERN NEOLOGISMS IN THE TEXTS

Shamsiddinova Shakhnoza Yakhyo kizi

Student of Master's department, Karshi state university

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Abstract. *The vocabulary of each country is constantly changing and developing in different ways. This process reflects the global nature of language and communication. It shows how quickly the use of new words or meanings can move from one end of the globe to the other. English neologisms, marked by online English dictionaries for the period 2016-2019, became the object of study of this article. Media occupies an important place among the intermediaries in the dissemination of new words. Journalists can be the authors of neologisms, and like news editions, they can open up new prospects for the use of various neologisms.*

Keywords: *Media, texts, neologism, novelty, pragmatic, potential.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ НЕОЛОГИЗМЫ В ТЕКСТАХ

Аннотация. *Лексика каждой страны постоянно меняется и развивается по-разному. Этот процесс отражает глобальный характер языка и коммуникации. Он показывает, как быстро использование новых слов или значений может перемещаться с одного конца земного шара на другой. Объектом исследования данной статьи стали английские неологизмы, отмеченные онлайн-словарями английского языка за период 2016-2019 гг. СМИ занимают важное место среди посредников в распространении новых слов. Журналисты могут быть авторами неологизмов и, подобно новостным изданиям, могут открыть новые перспективы использования различных неологизмов.*

Ключевые слова: *Медиа, тексты, неологизмы, новизна, прагматика, потенциал.*

A new word in the text of the newspaper goes through the stage of socialization. In addition, semantic novelty gives rise to pragmatic novelty. The material for the study was the online media texts of high-quality British and American newspapers. This allows us to obtain a detailed understanding of the specifics of neologisms and allows us to trace the level of productivity of their use in the two main diatonic versions of the English language. The results obtained indicate that there is a consistent pattern before lexicographers begin to observe an interest in the society for new words it takes at least 3-4 years. The same trend is observed when using neologisms on the pages of quality newspapers. Sometimes a new lexical unit gets a stylistic connotation. The dynamics of the use of lexical innovations is cyclical in connection with the importance of the problems that arise in society.

Modern life requires the study of all that is new in language. Like any language, English is experiencing a "neological boom." There are a number of definitions for the term "neologism." According to Cambridge English Dictionary, it is "a new word or expression, or a new meaning for an existing word". In researches, scientists often use the term "coinage" (Crystal, 2002). Neologisms — newly coined words or new senses of an existing word — are constantly being introduced into a language (Algeo, 1980). An ever-growing stream of new names contributes to a significant expansion of the neological space of the language (Katermina, 2017).

The field of neology has attracted the attention of linguists for more than a dozen years. A large number of research papers are devoted to the study and analysis of neologisms. Literature review revealed that the majority of research studies on neologisms belong to the field of linguistics. They are based on five theories, which define neologisms from different perspectives: stylistic theory (Ratsiburskaya & Solovyeva, 2018; Rets, 2014); denotation theory (Ulanova, 2014); structural theory (Toropkina, 2019); etymological theory (Cook, 2010); lexicographic theory (Yashina & Polyakova, 2017). Nevertheless, the specificity of the object under study is such that the topic does not exhaust itself, and research works continue to be relevant.

Media quickly respond to the emergence of new objects and phenomena of the world. However, one should not forget that in the modern communicative environment new types of media behavior of people have arisen (Kondrashkina & Maslova, 2018). A media text, like any other text, is a concrete act of communication and is one of the most common forms of the language's modern existence. Its main feature is that its ultimate goal is not only communication of information, but also a certain impact on the reader, that is, his pragmatic orientation (Terekhova et al., 2018). Thus, in the course of the study, it is important to consider the functioning of neologisms as a communicative-pragmatic means in media texts, and to study the factors of linguistic and cultural conditionality of their application. It allows us to obtain a more detailed understanding of the specifics of the occurrence of neologisms and to trace the level of productivity of their use in the two main diatonic versions of the English language, therefore, media texts from the high-quality press of the United States and Great Britain were chosen for the study.

The quantitative ratio of lexical units according to the thematic division was calculated within one year, where the total annual indicator corresponded to 100%. The most popular are the words and phrases associated with forms of social communication and behaviour, for example, "echo chamber", "gaslighting", "influencer", "mic drop", "milkshake duck", "orbiting", etc. In addition, many of the studied words have their roots in political or activist circles, for example;

“entryist”, “cakeism”, “youthquake”, “take a knee”, etc. They clearly reflect the heightened emotional and political state in which many people currently live.

The rapidly growing interest of the English-speaking society in the problems of ecology, environment and climate is obvious. It was just clear that issues relating to the climate were running through all the different lexical items. Oxford Dictionaries has named “climate emergency” as its 2019 Word of the Year, choosing it from an all-environmental shortlist that also included “climate action,” “climate denial,” “eco-anxiety,” “extinction” and “flight shame .” The use of the term “climate emergency” increased by a hundredfold since 2018, according to data collected in the Oxford Corpus. In fact, it was the most common compound involving “emergency.”

Thus, having highlighted not only popular, but also new formations within thematic groups, we turned to the study of their pragmatic potential on the basis of English-language quality newspapers. The corpus of the English texts of the newspaper discourse served as the material of this research, namely the articles presented by the sites of the high-quality British and the American newspapers such as “The Guardian”, “Independent”, “New York Times”, “The Washington Post”.

Neologization is a complex process. Gradually, the conceptual sphere of the language is updated with the transformation of society and the changing of the previously existing picture of the world (Ionova, 2016). Thus, we use the descriptive-analytical method, which includes a chronological criterion that indicates the emergence and functioning of neologism in the modern period of development of society and language. As well as a functional criterion that takes into account the denotative relevance of a new word to indicate a new reality (object, phenomenon, and concept).

The Oxford English Dictionary has called “post-truth” the international word in 2016. According to the publisher, the concept of post-truth has existed for the past decade, but in 2016, it became widespread. The term is a semantic euphemism implying the presence of false, inaccurate and false information in journalistic works (Ershov, 2018). In 2017, the phrase “fake news” was the phrase of the year according to Collins English Dictionary, since its frequency of use over this period increased by 365%. In 2019, Collins English Dictionary included “deepfake” in the shortlist of the year. “Deepfake” is a technical term. However, many areas of life are closely interconnected, the growing pragmatic potential of this word is obvious. Therefore, “fake news”, “post - truth” and “deepfake” are the pressing issues in modern society (Chudinov et al., 2019).

According to our research, the use of neologism “fake news” on the pages of online versions of American newspapers, such as The New York Times, The Washington Post, has almost doubled annually over the past three years, starting from 2018. However, in The Guardian and Independent, the combination of “fake news” is much less in demand, but the number of articles using this combination in 2019 has increased significantly compared to 2018 in the framework of its own corpus. Thus, the phrase “fake news” is linked with American journalism not only historically, but also in terms of usage dynamics, it is widely used in the American media. Moreover, the phrase “post - truth” is more often used in the British media. In particular, the pages of The Guardian recorded more articles with its use in 2017 and in 2019, even compared to Independent. On the pages of Independent, the phrase was very popular in 2016. In fact, “post – truth” in the modern mediated world is perceived as a communicative process and is used not only in connection with political events and events, but also acts as an ideological background in exposing inaccurate information of any format. Thus, in a crisis of objective fact, new words continue to arise.

This approach to the study of neologisms in various language variants in modern linguistics is important not only from the point of view of a purely descriptive study of neologisms and the systematization of productive methods, but also to the establishment of trends and patterns in the formation of new words from the point of view of a communicative-pragmatic approach. Clearly, the use of neologisms in media texts ties the narrative to modern times. Most of neologisms describe mainly political issues, economic problems, trends in the development of modern technologies, social phenomena of society.

However, not all new words that have been marked by well-known dictionary editions everywhere on both sides of the Atlantic in a given time period will be added to the main corpus of dictionaries. In addition, not all of these words are popular, relevant and in demand in the media sphere and, in particular, in media texts. In the era of global mediatisation and changed conditions of communication, high-quality editions cannot ignore the emerging new lexical units, since neologisms with their inherent topicality designate processes, objects and phenomena in the life of modern society. Our study showed that after the word was noted from the point of view of its widespread use, a certain period might pass when neologism becomes popular among authors of media texts. Because the relevance of neologisms for journalists is directly related to their pragmatic markedness. Sometimes a new lexical unit gets a stylistic connotation that limits its application. Besides, the dynamics of the use of new words is cyclical in connection with the importance of the problems that arise in society. Interest in neologisms of past years may change,

their relevance may increase, and lexical innovations that are similar in meaning may appear. Then, over time, we can talk about the appearance of hyponyms and hyperonyms in relation to the already known lexical units. Therefore, the study of neologisms in different languages has even greater prospects.

REFERENCES

1. Chudinov, A. P., Koshkarova, A. A., & Ruzhentseva, N. B. (2019). Linguistic interpretation of Russian political agenda through fake, deepfake, post-truth. *Journal of Siberian Federal University. Humanities & Social Sciences*, 12(10), 1840–1853.
2. Collins English Dictionary. (2019). <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english>
3. Terekhova, E. V., Savintseva, S. I., & Zban, A. V. (2018). Spetsifika diskursivnogo razvertyvaniya angloyazychnogo massmediynogo teksta [English Mainstream Texts and Specifics of Their Discourse Expansion]. *Scientific dialogue*, 6, 43-56.
4. [Common Similarities and Differences of Uzbek and English Fairy Tales](#)
KS Jalilovna *European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education*
2 (1), 366-369
5. [PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION](#) S Khalilova *Gospodarka i Innowacje*.
28, 6-11
6. [COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH FAIRY TALES](#) KS Jalilovna
IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 80-83
7. [A CASE STUDY ON VOCABULARY LEARNING THROUGH READING FAIRY TALES](#) KS Jalilovna *E-Conference Globe*, 5-6
8. [THE VALUE OF THE HERITAGE OF ABU ALI IBN SINA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH EDUCATION](#) S Khalilova *American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences* 14, 146-151
9. [The act of performance of fairy tales and traditions of storytelling](#) S Khalilova *ACADEMICIA an International Multidisciplinary research Journal*, 72-75
10. [Common features between the genres of English and Uzbek folklore](#) S Khalilova *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 323-327
11. Ganiyeva, M. (2023). THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPING THE LOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS (IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS). *Science and innovation*, 2(B3), 30-33.

12. Ganieva, M. (2023, June). EMPOWERING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TIPS TECHNOLOGY. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 62-63).

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